

How To Document Your Service

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Purpose

Service Documentation: documents, wiki pages, tutorials and other material describing your Base4NFDI service development and functionalities.

Thorough and structured service documentation is crucial in building a **sustainable** service that is **adopted** by the community. It helps users, administrators, and developers to...

- Set up the service
- Understand the user interface
- Get help while troubleshooting
- Follow best practices & prevent mistakes

But also...

- Align expectations as to what the service is / is not
- Navigate the wealth of information related to your service and allow to find specific information easily
- Keep track of progress, versions and the service development lifecycle

The documentation **structure and criteria outlined in this document are strongly recommended** in order to make Base4NFDI service documentations serviceable, comparable and easy to navigate.

Target Groups for Documentation

Before you start writing, consider **which target group needs to be able to understand and navigate your documentation**. What prerequisite knowledge do they have? How much time can they take to find information? Will they be in the middle of a task or need a structured onboarding to set up a service for their community?

In the Base4NFDI context, you will probably deal with one or both of the below:

- **Technical documents** targeted at developers, describing code structure, repositories, API documentation, required 3rd party software and more
- **User & Admin Guides**, describing the user interface, functionality and tasks related to the service

Where can you host your documentation?

Once your project has been accepted for the initialization phase, you will be given a github repo. Please send us an email to include your team members.

Please let us know if different repositories should be installed for e.g. a) code, b) knowledge management, c) documentation.

You can use a markdown interpreter/ static site generator such as Mkdocs, Docsify, Jekyll, or Docusaurus (check examples at the end of this document). Documentation pages can be written in Markdown. Ideally, all pages are located in the **docs** folder.

If you need support, please contact us at base4nfdi-office@lists.nfdi.de.

Guiding Principles for Quality Assurance

- **Keep it simple** – scrap irrelevant or redundant information
- **Avoid jargon** – wherever possible, use plain English, give a short definition if you need to use a technical term and resolve non-trivial acronyms on first usage
- **Give context** at the beginning of the document and at the beginning of each chapter. Think about your readers needs and pre-requisite knowledge
- **Don't rush it** – plan first, then write, then edit
- **Ask for feedback from the target groups** – this will allow you to evaluate how well the documentation serves its purpose, ask if they can find the information they are looking for, if it gives enough details / is complete and understandable. During writing, think about your user personas and how they would use the documentation.
- **Make it searchable** – test the search and make sure the results returned are meaningful
- **Create a new version regularly** – plan time regularly to make updates based on advancement of the service (with every “release”) or user feedback (e.g. every quarter). Consider if previous versions of the service are still used and previous documentation versions still need to be kept available (e.g. for users of previous version, migration tests, reinstallation etc.).

... and **highlight changes made from the previous version** – target groups (users, developers, IT administrators) will want to quickly see which relevant parts changed from the previous version. As a best practice, add a table with the changes made in the document (e.g. added section 5.6.7; edited Shell command on page 18)

Wherever possible, service documentation should be openly licensed under CC-BY.

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Recommended Structure (adapt as needed)

1. **What is...**
 - a. Purpose / Definition
 - b. Reference to Base4NFDI (incl. logo) & funding numbers
 - c. Metadata to identify and access the service (eg. name, hosting legal entity, classification information, ...)
 - d. Target group of the document with most relevant chapters per group
 - e. Version of the service that is described
 - f. Date this documentation had its last update
2. **Getting Started**
 - a. First steps as a member of the target group (there might be a different Getting Started for Admins vs. Users for example)
 - b. Typical Getting Started topics
 - i. Setup / Installation
 - ii. Login
 - iii. Account Settings / Configuration
 - iv. Basic Navigation
3. **Tutorials**
 - a. Create a navigation that represents typical tasks in a meaningful hierarchy (e.g. chronologically), structure by user segment – e.g. Tutorials for Repository Managers, Tutorials for Admins
 - b. For each task, you might use the following structure
 - i. User Segment or technical User Role
 - ii. Prerequisites
 - iii. Step by Step tasks
 - iv. Add screenshots, charts and visuals where relevant (but be careful – updating is time consuming, so avoid where possible)
4. **Release Notes**
 - a. New features, bug fixes ... by release date / version
5. **Architecture**
 - a. Technical documentation
 - b. Architecture diagrams
 - c. Attribute tables
6. **API documentation (if applicable)**
7. **Policies**
 - a. An up to date list of the policies that apply to the use of your service
8. **Contact**
 - a. Reference to project team, community sites, mailing list
9. **Further information**
 - a. Link Requirement documents and published results from surveys
 - b. Link Design documents

Examples

Base4NFDI Documentation:

- <https://doc.nfdi-aa.de/> (Mkdocs static site generator, self-hosted)

Examples for Knowledge Bases based on github in the NFDI:

- <https://github.com/NFDI4Microbiota/nfdi4microbiota-knowledge-base> (using Jekyll)
→ <https://knowledgebase.nfdi4microbiota.de/>
- https://github.com/NFDI4Chem/knowledge_base/blob/main/docs/00_intro/00_intro.mdx
(using Docusaurus)
→ https://knowledgebase.nfdi4chem.de/knowledge_base/docs/intro/

Some Examples for User Guides & Technical Documentation - for inspiration:

- (functional) <https://support.whatfix.com/docs/what-is-whatfix>
- (functional) https://help.salesforce.com/s/articleView?id=sf.cg_concept_understand_basemodel.htm&type=5
- (functional) <https://www.canva.com/help/downloading-saving-and-sharing/>
- (technical) <https://docs.docker.com/get-started/overview/>
- (technical) <https://devcenter.heroku.com/articles/getting-started-with-python>

Questions? Reach us any time at base4nfdi-office@lists.nfdi.de